

Origin of groundwater salinity in the Fasa Plain, Southern Iran, Hydrogeochemical and isotopic approaches

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Abstract

The study area, the Fasa Plain, is situated in the semi-arid region of Fars Province in the south of Iran. The Salloo diapir is a salt dome that crops out in the northwest of the study area. Isotopic and hydrochemical analyses were used to examine the water and how the origin of salinity and the diapirs affect the quality of the groundwater in the study area. Groundwater was sampled from 31 representative pumping wells and 5 springs in order to measure their stable isotope compositions, bromide ion concentration, and physical and chemical parameters. The alluvial aquifer was organized into two main groups based on the chemistry, with Group 1 consisting of low salinity samples (544-1744 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) with water type Ca-Mg-HCO₃-SO₄, which were taken in the center and north of the area, and Group 2 consisting of high salinity samples (2550-4620 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) with water type Ca-Mg-Cl-SO₄, which were taken in the south and southwest of the area. A saline spring near the salt dome with an EC of 10280 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ has water type NaCl, while the composition of the water in the other karstic springs is comparable to the fresh groundwater samples. All groundwater samples are undersaturated with respect to gypsum, anhydrite, and

halite, and are supersaturated with respect to calcite and dolomite. Stable isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$) differentiated four water types: saline springs, freshwater spring, fresh groundwater and saline groundwater. The results indicate that meteoric water is the main origin of these water resources. Halite dissolution from the salt dome was identified as the origin of salinity. The Na/Cl and Cl/Br ratios confirmed the results. Groundwater compositions in the southwestern part of the area are affected by the intrusion of saltwater from the salt dome. The average rate of saltwater intrusion in the observation wells is about 0.2%. In the south and southwestern part of the area, the saltwater fraction is positive in mixed fresh/salt water (Group 2). Different processes interact together to change the hydrochemical properties of Fasa's alluvial aquifers. The main processes that occur in the aquifer are mixing, gypsum dissolution, and calcite precipitation.

Keywords: Hydrogeochemistry, stable isotope, salt dome, salinity, karstic spring, groundwater

1. Introduction

Groundwater is used as the main source of domestic water in the arid and semi-arid regions of Iran. Access to good quality drinking water is the most basic human need but it is not always available in the most arid and semi-arid regions. These groundwater resources are currently studied through geochemical and hydrogeological research (Londoño et al., 2008; Kim et al., 2003; Adams et al., 2001). The composition of the groundwater varies naturally due to different factors such as rainfall composition, evaporation, oil-field brine and lithology (Zuhair, 2001). The Hormuz Formation, which crops out as a salt dome, is one of the important evaporites that can change the quality of adjacent groundwater. The quality of some groundwater in the south of Iran is affected by exposure to the more than 130 salt diapirs of the Hormuz Formation (Precambrian-Middle Cambrian), which is considered as a major potential origin of salinity (Bagheri, et al., 2013; Zarei et al., 2014). Consequently, the increase of chloride concentrations in

groundwater can be attributed to the impact of the saline layers of these salt diapirs and/or oil-field brine. Hydrochemical data in combination with environmental isotope techniques have commonly been used to evaluate the chemical characteristics of groundwater and its flow parameters (Yang et al., 2016; Gunnarsdottir et al., 2016; Bagheri et al., 2014; Wen et al., 2005). ^{18}O and ^2H stable isotopes are the most commonly applied parameters to distinguish meteoric and marine origins of formation waters (Clark and Fritz, 1997; Clayton et al., 1966; Yidana et al., 2010). In most cases, the drinking and domestic water supplied in southern Iran, especially in Fars Province, are in contact with the evaporites during recharge-storage-circulation-discharge stages as a result of the widespread occurrence of these rocks throughout the region. Therefore, the water quality is adversely affected by these geologic units. A few studies focus on the effect of salt diapirs on the groundwater quality in southern Iran (Bagheri et al. 2013a, 2013b; Raeisi et al. 1996; Sharafi et al. 2002; Zarei et al. 2014).

The Fasa Plain is situated near a salt dome in the semi-arid region of Fars Province, Iran. Groundwater is the most important source of domestic water in this region. The main objectives of this study are: (1) hydrochemical and isotopic evaluation of the water resources; (2) establish the water and salinity origins; (3) identify the processes that control the concentration of major constituents in the groundwater, and consequently, (4) assess the effect of the salt dome on the characteristics of the groundwater.

2. Study Area

Fasa Plain is located in Fars Province in the southeast of Iran ($53^{\circ}30'$ to $53^{\circ}50'$ E and $28^{\circ}50'$ to $29^{\circ}00'$ N) and covers an area of approximately 383 km^2 . Morphologically, it is composed of a plain surrounded by mountains. Neogene and Quaternary deposits in the Fasa Plain are bound by a few high karstic anticlines called Tudeh, Kulah-Qazi, and Gach and Khomar in the eastern, southwestern and southern parts of the area respectively. The water resources in Fasa Plain consist of an alluvial aquifer and some freshwater and saline springs. In a few parts of the

aquifer, the quality of the groundwater is compromised. The salinity source of the water in the spring and groundwater may be attributed to evaporation, halite dissolution and/or less likely oil-field brine. There is a gas reservoir not very far from the Fasa Plain, and there may even be another reservoir in the area that affects the quality of the groundwater. The Salloo diapir crops out near the plain in the northwest of the area and is the most probable cause of salinity. The groundwater resources should be protected against salinization in such a semi-arid region. The creation of protection strategies against contamination requires knowledge of the hydrogeological setting as well as of the quality of the groundwater. The mean annual precipitation is approximately 260 mm with a peak between December and February. Based on a report published by the Department of Agriculture in Fasa (2016), the mean annual temperature and evaporation is 17.7°C and 1880.4 mm respectively.

3. Geological and hydrogeological settings

Fasa plain is situated in the Zagros Mountains Range, which consists of a series of sub-parallel, NW-SE trending anticlines and synclines (Alavi, 2004; Stocklin and Setudehnia, 1977). The exposed geological formations, in descending order of age, are the Hormuz salt formation (Palaeozoic); the Sarvak limestone formation (Cretaceous); the Pabdeh-Gurpi shales and gypsiferous marl formation (Paleocene-Oligocene); the Sachun gypsum formation (Paleocene-Eocene); the Asmari-Jahrom limestone and dolomite formation (Oligocene-Miocene); the Razak evaporite formation (Miocene); the Gachsaran gypsum and marl formation; the Aghajari sandstone formation (late Miocene to Pliocene); the Bakhtiari conglomerate formation (late Pliocene-Pleistocene); and recent alluvium (Fig. 1). A few faults are found in the western and southern parts of the study area, which have probably caused the Hormuz Formation to crop out. The study area is situated in the Quaternary alluvial plain. The deposits in the center of the area are mainly sandy loam and silt, while the sediments near the edges are gravel and sand. The aquifer system that has developed in highly permeable karstified carbonate rocks often

discharges groundwater through springs. The alluvial aquifer in the area recharges mainly by subsurface groundwater inflows from the adjacent carbonate rocks and by rainfall. The groundwater generally flows from the north to the south of the plain (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1: Geological map and water sampling locations

Fig. 2: Iso-Potential map of the study area

4. Sampling and methods

Groundwater was sampled from 31 representative pumping wells and 5 springs during a survey in July 2014 (Fig. 1). Before sampling, the bottles were washed with distilled water. Water samples were collected in 300 mL dark PVC bottles. The electrical conductivity (EC) and pH were measured in situ by portable HANNA Multi-range EC Meter-HI8733 and AZ pH Meter-8601 respectively. Major ions were analyzed at the hydrogeology and geochemistry Laboratory of Shahrood University of Technology. Sulfate was determined by turbidimetric methods. Chloride, calcium and magnesium were measured by titration with EDTA. Sodium and potassium were determined by Sedico Ltd. - AFP-100 Flame Photometer. Bicarbonate was measured by titration with HCl. The ion balance (IB) was calculated to evaluate the quality of the analyses as follows:

$$IB = \{(\text{sum of cations} - \text{sum of anions}) / (\text{sum of cations} + \text{sum of anions})\} \times 100$$

(1)

where all ions are in meq/L. All analyses have $IB < 5\%$.

The saturation indices (SI) of the water samples with respect to different minerals were calculated using PHREEQC software (Parkhurst and Appelo, 1999).

$SI < 0$ and $SI > 0$ reflect undersaturation and supersaturation respectively, and $SI = 0$ is the equilibrium between the mineral and the solution. Twenty-five grab samples (60 mL) were collected in dark bottles to study the isotopic behavior of the different water resources in the study area and analyzed for ^{18}O and ^2H in the Stable Isotope Laboratory of the Atomic Energy Agency of Iran. The results are reported in ‰ relative to the VSMOW standard.

5. Results and discussion

The dominant reactions and geochemical processes that control the chemistry of the water resources in the area were identified using different methods, including

graphs and molar ratios of ions. The general hydrochemistry of the springs is discussed first. The cause of the salinity of the water resources and the effect of the salt dome on the characteristics of the groundwater are determined using geological, hydrochemical and isotopic tools.

5.1. General hydrochemistry

The origin of salinity and the hydrochemistry of the alluvial aquifer and carbonate springs in the Fasa Plain were investigated. The major element concentrations are displayed in Table 1. The EC of the groundwater samples ranges from 544 to 4619 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ with a mean value of 1316 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The mean concentrations of Mg, Ca, Na and K are 19.5, 27.5, 3.38 and 0.07 meq/L respectively. The concentration of SO_4 in the study area ranges from 0.7 to 37.1 meq/L. The Cl^- ion concentration ranges from 1 to 17.5 meq/L. The relative abundance of ions is $\text{Mg} > \text{Ca} > \text{Na} > \text{K}$ and $\text{SO}_4 > \text{HCO}_3 > \text{Cl}$ (in meq/L units) (Table 1). Piper diagram analysis was used to evaluate the geochemical evolution and the water type of the groundwater at the study area (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Piper diagram showing the hydrochemical classification of waters from the study area

From the north and west to the south, the waters evolve from a water type of mainly $\text{Ca-Mg-HCO}_3\text{-SO}_4$ (Group 1) to a water type of Ca-Mg-Cl-SO_4 (Group 2). The water samples were also plotted on a $(\text{CO}_3+\text{HCO}_3)\text{-(Cl+SO}_4)$ vs. $(\text{Ca+Mg})\text{-(Na+K)}$ graph

(Chadha, 1999) in order to classify and interpret the geochemical characteristics of the natural water samples (Fig. 4). Based on the graph, the water samples are water types Ca-Mg-HCO₃ and Ca-Mg-Cl. Basically, the groundwater samples can be classified into two main groups 1 and 2. In Group 1, the dominant cations and anions in the recharge zone are Ca-Mg and SO₄ and then HCO₃ respectively. Group 2, which has a higher salinity value, has an abundance order of Ca > Mg > Na > K and SO₄ > Cl > HCO₃. Almost all discharge springs in the study area have low EC values (between 300 and 500 μS/cm) and low discharge rates (0.1 to 2 L/s) (Table 1) with one exception: a saline spring that discharges near the salt dome with a discharge rate of 2 L/s and an EC value 10280 μS/cm. The Piper diagram shows that the saline spring has water type NaCl. On the (CO₃+HCO₃)-(Cl+SO₄) vs. (Ca+Mg)-(Na+K) graph, the saline spring also shows to have water type NaCl while other springs are similar to the fresh groundwater samples.

Fig. 4: Diagram showing the geochemical classification of groundwater (after Chadha, 1999)

The EC map (Fig. 5) shows a trend of increasing EC values from north to the south of the basin, especially toward the west. The TDS value also shows the same trend. As expected, the Cl and SO₄ value distributions in the basin show a pattern similar to the EC map. The temperatures and pH values of groundwater vary from 15 to 22°C and 7.18 to 8.82 respectively.

- Cluster analysis

Water/rock interaction and cation exchange are the main determinants of groundwater quality. Cluster analysis as a simple method is used to organize groundwater samples into separate hydrochemical groups based on water quality data (Belkhiri, 2012). The SPSS software (SPSS Inc. Released 2009) is used to statistically analyze the hydrochemical behavior of water samples. Ion species Ca, Mg, Na, K, Cl, SO₄ and HCO₃ were considered for cluster analysis. Results show that the sampled wells would be best separated into two homogeneous groups. Cluster 2 includes samples with high salinity (11, 15, 16, 17, and 18) found in the south and southwest of the basin near the salt dome. The rest of the samples with lower salinity fall into Cluster 1 and are mainly located in the recharge and central parts of the basin (Table 2).

Fig. 5: Iso-EC map of the alluvial aquifer

5.2. Origin of salinity and salt dome effect

5.2.1. Hydrochemistry method

- *Na/Cl and Cl/Br ratios*

The Na/Cl and Cl/Br ratios are used to distinguish halite dissolution from oil-field brine (evaporated paleo-seawater) as a source of salinity. The Na/Cl molar ratio and Cl/Br weight ratio resulting from the salt dissolution process are about 1 and more than 286 respectively (Bagheri et al., 2014; Richter and Kreitler 1993). The Na/Cl molar ratio and Cl/Br weight ratio measured in the saline spring and groundwater are about 1 and more than 300 respectively, confirming halite dissolution and not oil-field brine as the origin of salinity. The alluvial aquifer water in this region is near the Salloo diaper (Fig. 6). The saline water of the salt dome, which is at a shallower level than the groundwater below, probably flows through faults in the southwest of the area to increase the salinity.

Fig. 6: Schematic hydrogeological cross section of the study area

- *Saturation state*

Different types of information can be obtained from saturation data such as the equilibrium between the host minerals and the precipitation process. Table 1 shows the saturation index of the water samples. Nearly all water samples are supersaturated with respect to calcite and dolomite and undersaturated with halite and gypsum. The dissolution of Asmari limestone and dolomite rocks is the main source of calcium and magnesium ions in the groundwater. The prevailing lithology in the Fasa area is the Asmari-Jahrum carbonate formation, which consists of limestone and dolomite. The springs have low water discharges and are

supersaturated just like the alluvial aquifer. The presence of the bicarbonate ion (HCO_3^-) in the groundwater samples is due to the dissolution of carbonate rocks.

5.2.2. Isotopic method

^{18}O and ^2H isotope data from the saline and fresh karstic springs and fresh and saline groundwater samples are plotted in Fig. 7 along with the global and local meteoric water lines (GMWL and LMWL). The origin of fresh and saline karstic springs is meteoric water and the source of salinity of the saline spring is halite dissolution, not the oil-field brine, because the saline spring is located close to LMWL. Also, with increasing salinity of the samples, the ^{18}O values show almost constant behavior, confirming halite dissolution as the origin of salinity and ruling out the evaporation process. The groundwater samples in the study area plot near the LMWL with a small shift, indicating meteoric water as the main origin of the water with a little evaporation. As expected, the saline water samples have $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values within the range of both fresh groundwater and the saline spring water. The saline groundwater samples plot on a mixture line between the fresh groundwater and the saline spring water, indicating the intrusion of saline water from the salt dome in the southwest of the basin.

Fig. 7: The $\delta^2\text{H}$ versus $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ isotopes of the water samples

5.2.3. Fresh/salt water mixing

As mentioned above, the salt dome in the west of the basin can affect the quality of the groundwater. The saline spring confirms that it does. Groundwater compositions in the southwestern part of the area are also affected by the intrusion of salt water through this salt dome. Physicochemical analysis was used to evaluate the main processes that affect the quality of the groundwater in the Fasa Plain during fresh water/salt water mixing. The concentration of an ion i by conservative mixing of salt water and fresh water is:

$$m_{i, \text{mix}} = f_{\text{salt}} \cdot m_{i, \text{salt}} + (1 - f_{\text{salt}}) \cdot m_{i, \text{fresh}}$$

where f is the salt water fraction and m_i is the *ion* concentration in mmol/L (Appelo, 2005; Mondal et al., 2010). The intruded saline water fraction of each water sample was calculated using the Cl concentration of both freshwater and saltwater end-members:

$$f_{\text{salt water}} = (m_{\text{Cl, sample}} - m_{\text{Cl, fresh water}}) / (m_{\text{Cl, salt water}} - m_{\text{Cl, fresh water}})$$

In this study, it was assumed that the saltwater that is representative of the saline groundwater flowing from the salt dome toward the alluvium aquifer had a TDS of about 330 g/L due to the dissolution of halite from the salt dome. This can change the water quality during mixing. The freshest water sample in the study area is suggested as freshwater end-member in the formula. The calculated saltwater fraction in some water samples is shown in Table 3 and is about 0.2% on average. Due to the intrusion of saltwater in the south and southwest of the basin, the water samples in this area have a higher salinity than the other samples and are therefore classified in Group 2. Based on the below equation (Appelo, 2005; Fidelibus, 2003), the change in each ion concentration (m_{change}) is calculated as follows:

$$m_{\text{change}} = m_{i, \text{sample}} - m_{i, \text{mix}}$$

The m_{change} of Na, Ca, Mg and SO_4 was calculated for the saline springs of Group 2 (Table 3). The value indicates that some processes such as gypsum dissolution, calcite precipitation, mixing and dedolomitization processes act together to change the hydrochemical properties of the Fasa alluvial aquifers. These findings are further confirmed by the Piper diagram (Fig. 3). The multi-rectangular

Hydrochemical Facies Evolution Diagram (HFE-D) is applied to evaluate the hydrochemical facies during the freshening and intrusion stages (Fig. 8) (Gimenez Forcada, 2010). The freshwater and saltwater that belong to the Ca-HCO₃ and NaCl facies respectively are both the main end-members during the intrusion process. Ca and HCO₃ ions are the major ions in the fresh groundwater samples, while Na and Cl are the dominant ions in the saltwater samples. Geochemical processes such as cation exchange can take place when saltwater intrudes the freshwater aquifer or vice versa. The result is the characteristic Ca-Cl and Na-HCO₃ facies during both saltwater intrusion and freshening in the mixing zone (Appelo and Postma, 2005; Domenico and Schwartz, 1990; Ghiglieri et al., 2012; Hem, 1970). According to Fig. 8, a few water samples fall on the mixing line between freshwater and saltwater, but most of the samples depart from this mixing line, indicating cationic exchange reactions as well as other previously discussed processes.

Fig. 8: Hydrogeological Facies Evolution Diagram (HFE-D) for the water samples (after Gimenez Forcada, 2010)

6. Conclusions

In this study, 36 water samples from the alluvial aquifer and karstic springs in the Fasa Plain were measured in order to assess the hydrochemistry and stable isotope characteristics of the water resources. Based on the cluster analysis, Piper diagrams and $(\text{CO}_3+\text{HCO}_3)$ - $(\text{Cl}+\text{SO}_4)$ vs. $(\text{Ca}+\text{Mg})$ - $(\text{Na}+\text{K})$ graphs, two water groups were defined. Group 1 has a low EC value (mean EC = 1120 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) with an ionic order of $\text{Ca} > \text{Mg}$ and $\text{HCO}_3 > \text{SO}_4$. Group 2 Ca-Mg-Cl-SO_4 water type samples become more saline (mean EC = 3411 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). The source of salinity of the spring and groundwater may be attributed to evaporation, halite dissolution and/or, less likely, oil-field brine. Stable isotope analysis showed that meteoric water is the main origin of these water resources. Based on the hydrochemistry and isotopic results, the origin of salinity is defined as halite dissolution from the salt dome. Groundwater compositions in the southwest of the area are affected by saltwater intrusion from the Salloo diapir, which crops out in the northwest of the study area. The mean percent of saltwater intrusion to the sampled wells is about 0.2% during the mixing process. This study shows that it is very important to study groundwater characteristics and hydrogeochemical processes to improve the management of groundwater resources. Determining the water origin and salinity sources of these resources is complex, extremely delicate and difficult to deal with in karst hydrology, hydrogeology and geology due to the unknown geology and morphology of underground features. Unfortunately, there are no hydrogeological data between the salt dome and the alluvial plain, the hydraulic connection and groundwater flow direction, direct or indirect contact between the salt dome and alluvial aquifer, and the exact saltwater fraction in the water samples also remains uncertain. Multiple methods must be used to improve the interpretation of water origin and salinity sources.

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Sample ID	EC	pH	Ca	Mg	Na	K	HCO₃	Cl	SO₄	SI_A[*]	SI_C[*]	SI_D[*]	SI_G[*]
1	858	7.68	3.5	2.5	2.8	0.04	4.5	2.5	1.9	-1.94	0.43	0.85	-1.72
2	1053	7.73	4.5	4.1	2.2	0.05	3.8	3.2	3.8	-1.59	0.47	1.03	-1.37
3	1072	7.45	3.5	4.1	3.3	0.06	3.8	3.1	4.1	-1.68	0.09	0.37	-1.46
4	1180	8.41	2.5	5.2	4.3	0.06	3.5	3.3	5.1	-1.74	0.81	2.05	-1.52
5	1462	7.33	4.5	5.5	4.7	0.08	3.6	5.1	6.3	-1.45	0.01	0.23	-1.23
6	1462	7.34	6.1	6.1	2.8	0.08	4.5	4.8	5.5	-1.4	0.24	0.61	-1.18
7	877	7.94	2.5	2.8	3.6	0.04	4.1	3.1	1.9	-2.06	0.49	1.17	-1.84
8	1764	7.65	4.3	7.2	6.1	0.09	5.3	7.5	5.1	-1.60	0.46	1.28	-1.38
9	968	7.49	3.5	2.5	3.8	0.05	4.2	2.8	3.1	-1.75	0.17	0.33	-1.53
10	544	7.79	2.5	0.5	2.6	0.03	4.1	1.1	0.7	-2.39	0.41	0.25	-2.17
11	3899	7.18	27.5	19.5	3.1	0.14	3.5	4.5	34.8	-0.31	0.39	0.55	-0.09
12	1316	7.63	3.3	6.4	4.1	0.07	5.1	3.5	5.3	-1.64	0.32	1.06	-1.43
13	858	8.82	4.5	1.5	2.7	0.04	5.1	3.1	0.8	-2.22	1.63	2.92	-2.10
14	1611	7.65	8.6	8.9	1.2	0.08	6.2	4.5	7.4	-1.20	0.78	1.71	-0.98
15	2456	7.27	13.5	5.5	7.4	0.17	6.1	10	9.8	-0.94	0.56	0.86	-0.72
16	4619	7.73	20.1	17.5	11.1	0.25	5.2	17.5	26.8	-0.56	0.96	1.99	-0.34
17	3411	7.8	12.5	12.5	4.6	0.19	7.1	17.5	11.4	-1.04	1.06	2.44	-0.82
18	2778	7.24	15.1	12.1	2.8	0.16	6.1	10	12.8	-0.85	0.55	1.12	-0.64
19	1121	7.64	3.2	4.2	4.3	0.07	5.2	3.5	2.9	-1.87	0.34	0.93	-1.65
20	1122	8.10	3.1	2.5	5.8	0.06	3.5	2.7	5.2	-1.62	0.61	1.26	-1.40
21	1579	7.29	3.2	9.1	3.9	0.09	3.5	5.3	7.1	-1.61	-0.23	0.14	-1.39
Sp1	407	9.31	3.4	1.6	0.3	0.04	3.7	0.5	0.7	-1.84	1.94	3.71	-1.62
Sp2	502	9.52	4.1	1.8	0.4	0.04	4.1	0.5	1.1	-1.63	2.10	4.02	-1.41
Sp3	460	7.48	2.8	1.9	1.1	0.04	3.8	1.1	1.1	-1.77	0.36	0.68	-1.55
Sp4	1320	9.81	4.5	4.1	4.6	0.06	3.1	6.8	4.7	-1.11	1.97	4.03	-0.89
SP5(Saline)	10280	8.67	10.1	9.1	102.3	0.31	4.1	99.5	7.5	-0.95	1.61	3.32	-0.74

* SI_A, C, D and G means: Saturation index of Anhydrite, Calcite, Dolomite and Gypsum, respectively.

Table 1: Hydrochemical parameters for the shallow groundwaters and karstic springs in the study area (all concentrations are given in meq/L and EC in $\mu\text{S/cm}$), SI is dimensionless

	<i>Group 1</i>				<i>Group 2</i>			
	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD
EC	544	1764	1121	331	2456	4619	3411	867.14
Ca	2.5	8.6	3.5	1.5	0.25	12.50	0.17	0.04
Mg	0.5	9.1	4.1	2.5	5.50	19.50	12.50	5.45
Na	1.2	6.1	0.1	1.2	2.80	11.13	4.63	3.50
K	0.03	0.09	0.06	0.01	0.14	0.25	0.17	0.04
Cl	1.1	7.5	3.2	1.5	4.50	17.50	10.01	5.58
SO₄	0.7	7.4	4.5	2.1	9.79	34.81	12.77	11.08
HCO₃	3.5	6.1	4.1	0.7	3.50	7.02	6.04	1.32

Table 2: Parameter values of the two principal water groups (all concentrations are given in meq/L and EC in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)

Chemical constituents	Salt water (mmol/lit)	Fresh water (mmol/lit)	Well no.	Ionic changes (m_{change}) (mmol/lit)				
				Ca	Mg	Na	SO ₄	$f_{\text{saltwater}}$
Ca	18.5	1.7	11	12.1	5.4	-1.2	17.1	0.0008
Mg	60.7	0.8	15	5.1	1.8	-2.3	4.4	0.0019
Na	5085.1	0.3	16	8.2	7.7	-6.1	12.9	0.0033
K	47.41	0.04	17	4.5	8.7	-12.5	5.2	0.0033
HCO ₃	0.8	3.7	18	5.8	5.1	-6.9	5.9	0.0019
Cl	5125.1	0.5						
SO ₄	41.6	0.3						

Table 3: Ionic changes (m_{change}) of the selected ions and calculated saltwater fraction for saline wells (Group 2)